

ANALYSIS OF THE TRACE ELEMENT COMPOSITION OF TOOTHPASTES

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The aim of the study is to determine the micro- and macronutrient composition of toothpastes from various price categories using atomic emission spectral analysis to assess their safety and effectiveness.

Atomic emission spectral analysis is a method based on the study of the optical emission spectra of atoms that occur during the transition of electrons from excited energy levels to the main ones. During the analysis, the sample is atomized in a high-temperature plasma (4000 °C), after which the characteristic spectral lines of the elements are recorded. The method allows for qualitative and quantitative analysis of the elemental composition with high sensitivity and selectivity.

Materials and methods. The study was carried out on a DFS-452 spectrograph with a photodiode recording system. Paste samples were applied to carbon electrodes, excited in an arc discharge (18 A, 380 V), and then analyzed in the range of 190-1100 nm. The spectra were processed using the Atom software and a database of spectral lines.

Results

1. Toothpaste of high price category (Fig. 1)

- Macronutrients: Na, P, Si, Zn, Cr, Fe, Mn.
- Trace elements: Cu, Ni, Ti, Al, V.
- The absence of toxic elements (Pb, As, Hg)

Hg)

confirms compliance with standards.

2. Low price toothpaste:

- Macronutrients: Al, Ca, Na, Si, Zn.
- Trace elements: Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, P, Ti, V.

The increased content of Al (in the form of aluminum oxide) requires an additional assessment of the risks of accumulation in the body.

Useful elements were found in the studied samples: Ca, P, Zn, they contribute to the remineralization of enamel and have antibacterial properties, Si (SiO₂) is a safe, alternative abrasive. Elements contributing to potential risks: Al (Al₂O₃) is an alternative, more harmful abrasive, can bind phosphates, disrupting mineral metabolism, Cr and Mn are toxic in high concentrations.

The method confirmed the absence of toxic elements in the studied pastes, but revealed differences in the content of functional components. Expensive pasta shows a more balanced composition with a predominance of remineralizing and antimicrobial elements. The data obtained can be used to optimize toothpastes formulations, taking into account regional peculiarities (for example, mineral deficiency in the soft water of the Northwest).

